

CIRCUMSTANCES ARISING IN THE CULTIVATION OF HIGH-YIELDING BREEDS

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Livestock, consumption, santa-gertruda, Kazakh whiteheaded, red-desert, bushuev, food, clothing, meet, milk, cattle, blackand-white, aberdin - angus Cattle breeding, one of the main branches of animal husbandry, is developing steadily around the world.

ABSTRACT

Over the years, a comprehensive study of livestock products, their consumption, the level of exports and their opportunities, the level of demand has been extensively studied. Today, livestock is one of the leading and well-known sectors of the economy of the Republic. Indicators before and after the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan are analyzed in figures.

In all countries of the world, the breeding of specialized high-yielding breeds is carried out on a large scale. Of the cattle breeds in different regions of Uzbekistan, 4 are dairy and doubleproductive (black-and-white, red-desert, bushuev and hvis) and three are meat (santa-gertruda, Kazakh white-headed, aberdin - angus).

About 40% of cattle bred in Uzbekistan are black, 29% are red, 22% are brown, 3% are Bushuev and 6% are beef. If we describe the ancestral species of cattle (the last representative of which has not survived, the last one died in 1627 in the Mazowieck Zoo in Poland), it was a large animal with a strong body structure, strong horns, strong. The average height of bulls was 180-200 cm and that of cows was 160-175 cm.

Cattle breeds are divided into 3 groups depending on the direction of productivity.

I. Dairy breeds include Kara-Ala, Holmagor, Yaroslav, Avliyota, Bushuev, Red Desert and others.

1) Cattle of Kara-Ala breed are bred in all regions of the republic. Of the total number, the main part is fertilized in Tashkent, Fergana, Namangan, Syrdarya, Samarkand regions, and about 10% in Andijan, Bukhara, Surkhandarya and Khorezm regions. The color of the cattle is black and white, and the white belt on their chests is its distinctive feature.

Black-and-white cows are characterized by extremely high productivity (4000-6000 kg of milk, fat content 3.6-4.0%). The average live weight of adult cows is 500-550 kg, and the weight of pedigree bulls is 1000-1200 kg.

The Red Desert breed is bred in Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya, Khorezm, Navoi regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

The color of the cattle varies from light red to dark red. The weight of cows is 450-500 kg, and that of bulls is 800-900 kg. The milk yield of cows is 3000-5000 kg and the fat content is 3.8-3.9%.

Cattle belonging to the Bushuev breed are bred mainly in the Syrdarya region. The color of the cattle is white, with many small red or black spots all over the body, the ears and nose are dark black, and the body is elongated. Calves weigh 22-36 kg at birth, cows 440-550 kg and bulls 750-1000 kg. The milk yield of cows is 2500-3500 kg.

II. There are two productive breeds - Swiss, Alatov, Simmental and others.

The Swiss breed is bred in Andijan, Fergana, Namangan, Jizzakh, Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions. The Swiss breed is brown, ranging from light brown to dark brown. It has a dark beak and a light wool coat around it. Live weight of calves at birth is 31-38 kg, live weight of cows is 500-600 kg, and weight of bulls is 800-1000 kg. Each cow produces 3,500-4,000 kg of milk with a fat content of 3.8-3.9%.

Alatov breed. It was created in the Alatov foothills of Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. Cows weigh 550-580 kilograms, bulls 850-1000 kilograms, milk yield is 3549 kilograms and fat content is 3.4%. Slaughter expenses were 55-57%.

A breed of beef cattle. - Santa Gertruda, Kazakh white-headed, Hereford, Sharole, shortgorn and others.

Santa is a gertrude breed. Homeland is the district of Santa Gertruda, Texas, USA. In 1967, 11 bulls and 69 heifers were placed on the Bakhmal farm in the Jizzakh region of Uzbekistan. The weight of cows is 500-700 kg, bulls 950-1200 kg. The milk yield of cows is 1500-1800 kg, its fat content is 4.5-5.0%. Slaughter costs 60-66%. For every 100 cows, 82-84% of calves are obtained in Uzbekistan.

Kazakh white head breed. It is native to Kazakhstan and southeastern Russia. Calves weigh 27-30 kg, cows 500-550 kg, bulls 800-900 kg, and some 1100 kg. The milk yield of cows is 1200-1500 kg, the fat content is 3.8-4.0%. Slaughter costs 65-67%. Raising young calves is one of the main problems on livestock farms, and the production of productive cows depends to a large extent on the solution of these problems. Today, the herd is replenished by importing foreign-bred animals. However, given the fact that imported animals are difficult to adapt to local climatic conditions and are very expensive, it is important for the farm to improve the breed of the animals and to increase the pedigree of the calves in order to fill the herd in the future.

In well-developed farms, there is a need to regulate calving, that is, to have a calf at every month of the year.

If the farm has 100 head of cattle, it should consist of at least 30 cows, 6 heifers, 9 female calves older than 1 year, 15 female calves up to 1 year old, and they should be raised in separate groups. This will allow cows to be replaced every 6-7 years.

After calves are born, they should be separated according to their origin, and calves should be raised with special care in order to fill the herd in the future. To do this, newborn calves should be kept with their mothers for 15-20 days and adequate conditions should be created for them. Calves bred for breeding purposes should be fed only skim milk for up to 6 months, and an average of 250- 300 kg of skim milk should be given to 1 head of calf, during which time they are also taught to eat raw foods. This is because it is one of the factors influencing high productivity in animals.

There are 400 kilograms of food, 450 kg of poultry, 1440 kg of siflatli silos, 290 kg of silos, 1850 kg of meat, 650 kg of macaque, and 7.5 kg of meat.

Females older than one year need 450 kg of alfalfa hay, 925 kg of corn, 11 kg of salt, 450 kg of alfalfa hay per year, 180 kg of somoni, 272 kg of mixed fodder, 12 kg of salt.

The level of nutrient supply in females is assessed by determining their body weight gain. Female body weight should average 150 kg at 6 months, 250 kg at 1 year and 350 kg at 18 months. It is advisable that their body weight at the time of fertilization is 75-85% of the mother's body weight (average - 340-350 kg). In the rearing of female carcasses, of course, it is necessary to organize their distribution.

In order to replenish the herd, the separated offenders should be separated from the place of birth for 2 months, trained in the hands and massaged the udder once or twice a day. These measures will ensure a 15-25% increase in milk yield after childbirth. The offspring are transferred to the maternity ward 10 days before birth and are under veterinary supervision at birth.

Separate, clean and quiet places should be chosen for the delivery of puppies, and they should be provided with maternity equipment. The umbilical cord of a newborn calf is treated with disinfectants (iodine tincture) and stored with the mother for 15-20 days. After the calf is born, it is better to be licked by the mother, because when the mother licks with her tongue, the calf's reflexes to suck and stand up appear faster due to the action of receptors on the skin.

Before breastfeeding a calf, the mother's udder should be washed and dried with lukewarm water, the first batch of milk should be taken, and the udder should be assured of quality udder milk.

Calves should drink breast milk as early as possible, ie within 0.5-1 hours after birth, because the intestinal absorption of immunoglobulins in the udder lasts only 36 hours. Calves who consume breast milk late can be more susceptible to dyspepsia or other illnesses. When keeping calves with their mothers, of course, milk the cows 3-4 times a day, taking into account the needs of the calf. The average daily calf's need for milk in the first 10 days of life is 4 liters. After 15-20 days of keeping with the calf, the cows are transferred to the milking parlor, where their milk yield is determined, they are examined by a veterinarian, and when they are healthy, they are artificially inseminated. The average lactation period for cows is 305 days.

Cows are weaned 2 months before calving and reared in a separate group as long as possible. Good care of the cow during the weaning period will allow it to become more valuable and increase milk production!

How can a cow's disease be diagnosed in advance? This is done as follows: at the right time, read the right signs from the right cows. Take the time to evaluate the goods at least twice a day, taking into account the possible risks and their timing. Most problems are noted when the risk is high. In that case, be careful. High-risk groups include dairy cows and heifers because they go through a number of dangerous periods and farmers do not always pay attention to them when they need them. However, the future productivity of the herd depends on these goods.

There is a risk period for all goods or for goods on a particular farm. Such dangerous periods can occur on any farm: births, early days of life, sudden illness of calves, regrouping, lactation, dietary changes, group mixing, climate change, and so on. By going through the

cattle and discussing the basics of development, it is possible to identify certain periods of risk on the farm. Proper risk management will prevent them and ensure the future success of the farm.

Valuable information can be obtained by studying the growth schedule of calves. Falling growth rates indicate a risk. Differences in the growth of cattle of the same age may be due to different consumption of the disease and lactation. Are the animals underweight? So the reasons for this need to be clarified. Compare the growth of the neck with obesity. If the area around the chest is normal and there is an excess amount of fat in the body, fertilization will be negatively affected.

The following applies to most farm breeds:

- 45% onset of puberty
- 55% is a good time for fertilization
- 85% of birth weight

Measuring the chest is a convenient way to estimate body weight. If you do this regularly (more than twice a year), you will have accurate information about the growth of the cow and you will find out that the height of the cow has not grown enough.

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